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GAMEHEARTS

Concept Design Document

Project: Games, Heritage, Arts, & Sport: the economic, social, and cultural value of the European videogame ecosystem. GAMEHEARTS

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Executive Summary

Project Concept

This Concept Design Document (CDD) is the primary deliverable of Work Package 6, Task 2 (T6.2) of the GAMEHEARTS project, a Horizon Europe funded research initiative exploring how the European video game industry can collaborate with cultural institutions for mutual benefit and to create more inclusive and engaging experiences. The project involves five universities (Vienna, Salford, Tampere, Breda, Wrocław), industry partner Ubisoft, and three cultural partners: the London Symphony Orchestra (LSO), Imperial War Museums (IWM), and City Football Group (CFG).

Work Package 6 focuses on creating a video game that expands audience reach for the GAMEHEARTS project and delivers practical insights for cultural partners. This document presents the agreed concept that will be developed into a playable prototype in the next phase (T6.3).

The Collaborative Process

The concept emerged from structured dialogue rather than extraction of cultural content. Cultural partners were positioned as active collaborators whose priorities shaped the design from inception. The process involved:

- ♥ Individual consultations with each cultural partner to identify their unique goals: personal wartime stories (IWM), immersive musical experiences (LSO), and sports-centred engagement (CFG)
- ♥ An online ideation session that identified shared themes across all three institutions: growth through adversity, exploring spaces and relationships, collaborative play over competition, learning through gameplay, and meaningful narrative experiences
- ♥ A concept jam by the development team at Breda University of Applied Sciences using established design/ideation frameworks (Double Diamond method, Crazy Eight brainstorming)
- ♥ Integration of Target Audience Research from University of Salford and insights from Design Thinking Marathons ('DTthons') by Wrocław University, which identified terminology gaps between gaming and cultural sectors.

The resulting concept balances each partner's distinct vision with practical development constraints, demonstrating a viable collaboration model between video games and cultural sectors. It is ambitious in scope, but that ambition (and the ability to reach it) will provide a source of data for future projects.

The Game Concept

Core Idea: An environmental adventure, with rhythm-based sections, about a lonely football separated from its family during wartime, journeying home through war-torn Europe.

How It Works: Players control a small football that continuously rolls forward through three acts (Battlefield, Town, Wooded Highlands). Gameplay alternates between rhythm-driven movement synchronised to orchestral music and exploration-based puzzle-solving. The story unfolds without words through environmental design, using music and visuals to convey themes of loss, resilience, community, and hope.

Cultural Integration:

- ♥ **LSO contribution:** Orchestral music drives rhythm mechanics; players experience classical music as gameplay, not decoration
- ♥ **IWM contribution:** Semi-realistic wartime setting inspired by both World Wars; environmental storytelling emphasises civilians' experiences and historical authenticity
- ♥ **CFG contribution:** Football protagonist embodies themes of play, teamwork, and belonging; connects to football's community-building role.

The concept draws on established video game traditions (rolling-ball games like *Marble Madness*, *Super Monkey Ball*) while using cultural partnerships to create emotional depth that is unusual in this genre.

Meeting Project Objectives

Demonstrating Cross-Sector Collaboration: The concept proves that video games and traditional cultural sectors can work as equal partners when given structured frameworks and shared vocabulary. Each partner's priorities are authentically embedded in core mechanics rather than superficially applied.

Expanding Cultural Audiences: The design targets younger and more diverse audiences through accessible gameplay, wordless narrative (removing language barriers), and embedding cultural content within emotionally engaging play rather than educational frameworks. Target audience research informed four personas representing different player motivations and cultural partner priorities.

Integrating Diverse Cultural Domains: The concept identifies thematic common ground (human resilience, community, hope) across performing arts, heritage, and sports—domains that rarely explicitly intersect. It translates each partner's priorities into complementary design elements in a cohesive experience.

Building Research-Informed Practice: Design decisions were directly shaped by:

- ♥ Target Audience Research (University of Salford) identifying Explorer and Achiever player types and developing four user personas
- ♥ Design Thinking Marathon findings (Wrocław University) highlighting communication barriers, which prompted the glossary and careful language choices throughout documentation
- ♥ Each cultural partner's specific constraints functioned as productive design parameters.

Accessibility and Inclusion

Accessibility shaped the concept from its earliest stages:

- ♥ **Wordless narrative** removes language barriers
- ♥ **Dual level structure** (rhythm-based Highway levels and exploration-based Vignettes) offers varied pacing for different play styles
- ♥ **PC platform with gamepad controls** avoids console costs and allow for mid-range hardware specifications to assist technical accessibility
- ♥ **Simple control scheme** (movement, jumping, chiming) welcomes players unfamiliar with complex gaming inputs and supports accessibility controllers like Xbox Adaptive Controller
- ♥ **Camera and movement design** minimises motion sickness through centring the player view and limiting sudden shifts.

Technical Approach

- ♥ **Platform:** PC with gamepad (Xbox One controller standard)
- ♥ **Development:** Unreal Engine 5, targeting mid-range hardware specifications
- ♥ **Art Style:** Medium-poly 3D assets with 2D background layers; high-contrast visuals with bold silhouettes for clarity
- ♥ **Narrative Method:** Environmental storytelling; no dialogue or text
- ♥ **Game Structure:** Linear progression through three acts, each with distinct seasonal aesthetics (fall, winter, spring).

Next Steps and Evaluation

This concept document represents ambitious design intentions rather than tested outcomes. The intended audience engagement, cultural integration, and collaborative benefits remain propositional until the prototype is developed and evaluated. The next phase (T6.3) will translate this concept into a playable prototype, followed by implementation and testing (T6.4) that will provide empirical evidence of the approach's effectiveness.

The concept was presented at the GAMEHEARTS Conference at the Imperial War Museum, London, in October 2025.

Value for Stakeholders

For Cultural Partners: A model showing how institutions can integrate their content authentically into video game experiences to reach new audiences without compromising artistic or educational integrity.

For the Video Game Industry: Evidence that cultural partnerships can enhance rather than constrain creative design, demonstrating how meaningful collaboration produces distinctive games.

For Policy and Research Communities: A documented case study of structured cross-sector collaboration, including practical frameworks, communication strategies, and research-informed design methods applicable beyond this specific project.

For Horizon Europe: Tangible progress toward GAMEHEARTS objectives of maximising European video game industry ecosystem value within broader creative and cultural industries, with clear pathways for continued development and evaluation. The prototype will also serve as a demonstration of how typical R&D can result in non-traditional outcomes that speak the language of the humanities and culture.

Document Purpose

This Concept Design Document serves three functions:

1. **Development foundation** for programmers, artists, designers, and producers building the prototype
2. **Communication tool** between developers and cultural/academic partners
3. **Project deliverable** demonstrating Work Package 6, Task 2 completion for Horizon Europe review.

The document includes a comprehensive glossary to bridge terminology gaps between gaming and cultural sectors, which is a barrier identified through project research as a significant obstacle to effective collaboration.

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1. Project Summary

GAMEHEARTS seeks to maximise the value of the European video game industry ecosystems (hereafter, EVGIE) within a wider social context of the creative and cultural industries (hereafter, CCI). This considers the importance of the EVGIE in contributing to economic growth, job creation, physical and mental wellbeing, and social and cultural cohesion, by particularly focusing on how a stronger and closer working relationship between the traditional and emergent cultural sectors, can work better to create more inclusive and socially responsible cultural experiences. The consortium offers policy recommendations and roadmaps setting out the ways in which the EVGIE can and should develop, and where it could act as a driver for sustained innovation and economic growth. It utilises an evidence-based approach that focuses not just on video game development, but rather adopts a comprehensive ecosystem approach, working with both established and more innovative methodologies, to consider the competitiveness and development of the EVGIE, and the ways in which video game know-how and technologies could drive innovation in the wider CCI. In doing so, GAMEHEARTS explore 'ludic experiences', as ways to develop more inclusive, engaging, and empowering cultural experiences. Working across seven work packages the universities of Salford (UK), Tampere (Finland), Vienna (coordinator) (Austria), Breda University of Applied Sciences (Netherlands), and Wroclaw University of Economics and Business (Poland), will be working in partnership with Ubisoft (France), Imperial War Museum (UK), the City Football Group (UK), the London Symphony Orchestra (UK), and other major cultural and video game partners and associations to explore current and future trends in the EVGIE.

WP6 Summary

Work Package 6 focuses on creating video game experiences that expand audience reach and diversity for cultural partners. The work package is divided into four tasks: stakeholder and audience research (T6.1), producing ludic experiences brief (T6.2), creating the ludic experiences (T6.3), and implementing and testing them (T6.4).

This Concept Design Document is the primary deliverable of T6.2. During this phase, the development team at Breda University of Applied Sciences used established design methodologies, including the Double Diamond method and the Scrum Agile Framework, to create a high-level concept informed by research from earlier work packages and ongoing practice-led inquiry. The document captures discussions and agreed outputs from stakeholder interviews and audience research conducted by the University of Salford in T6.1, translating these insights into a creative brief for the development team. Following completion of this phase, the concept will move into T6.3 where it will be developed into a playable prototype.

2. About this Document

This document specifies the concept design for the game in development as part of the deliverables of Work Package 6 of the GAMEHEARTS project (Grant Agreement No. 101132543). As part of the production of Ludic Experiences, a Game Concept Design Document was developed based on the considerations, discussions and agreed outputs from the earlier phases of the GAMEHEARTS project.

A Game Concept Design Document (CDD) provides a concise overview of a game's core idea. Typically produced during the pre-production phase of development, the CDD serves as a foundational tool for presenting the overall game concept to investors, partners, and other stakeholders.

While specific contents vary, a CDD generally includes an introduction, background context, a description of the game concept, key features, genre classification, target platform(s), concept art, unique selling points, and target audience analysis. This list is not exhaustive, as no established industry standard dictates the precise contents of such documentation.

Given the dynamic nature of game development, the CDD functions as a living document, subject to continuous revision throughout the production cycle. Despite this variability, common practice favours brevity, emphasising only essential ideas and details to maintain clarity and focus. CDDs are frequently accompanied by pitch presentations that provide stakeholders with additional practical information regarding development logistics.

For this CDD, the development team at BUAs adopted a moderately detailed approach, reflecting the research-oriented nature of the project and core features outlined in the work package tasks. Consequently, the document extends beyond high-level conceptualisation to include target audience personas, technical specifications, core gameplay mechanics, audiovisual design considerations, and a narrative outline. The CDD will then serve as the base of concept for the next phase in the project: the development of the video game prototype, or ludic experience, and serve as an aid in the communication between the Video Game Development Team at Breda University of Applied Sciences and the cultural partners at London Symphony Orchestra, City Football Group and Imperial War Museum.

How to engage with this document

This document has three purposes. First, it is to serve as the base for the design to be used by the programmers, artists, designers and producers involved in the design, development, implementation and testing of the prototype of the game. Second, it functions as a communication tool between the developers and the cultural and academic partners within the GAMEHEARTS project. As this document is the main deliverable of Work Package 6, task 2, this document is additionally intended to be read by the reviewers of the GAMEHEARTS project. Third, it acts as a record of this process for future research teams interested in how creative practices, such as game development, can embody academic research.

This document outlines the concept for the game prototype intended for development by the team at BUas (Breda University of Applied Sciences) as part of the GAMEHEARTS project. In its current state as of January 2026, this CDD represents a snapshot of the concept as agreed upon through earlier phases of the study. These phases included collaborative discussions with the three cultural partners, an online ideation session, an internal concept jam, Target Audience Research conducted by the University of Salford, and insights from the Design Thinking Marathons facilitated by Wrocław University of Economics and Business. The details documented in this CDD have informed the Game Design Documentation (GDD) and will be iterated upon throughout development in response to feedback, testing outcomes, and evolving design decisions.

Document navigation

The document is sectioned as follows:

Project Summary provides a brief overview of the GAMEHEARTS project's goals, scope, and aims, followed by the specifications for Work Package 6: Building a Ludic Experience.

About This Document presents essential contextual information for readers prior to engaging with the concept design. This includes an explanation of the document's purpose, its position within the broader project framework, guidance on how to navigate its contents, and a glossary of terminology and acronyms commonly used in video game development.

About the Concept offers insight into how the concept was developed and how it aligns with the overarching objectives of the GAMEHEARTS project. This section also introduces the target audience and user personas and explains how principles of accessibility and inclusion have been embedded within the concept from its inception.

Overview of the Concept presents the foundational elements of the game, including its genre, setting, structure, player interaction model, core game loop, and an initial exploration of its intended aesthetic direction.

The subsequent sections provide progressively greater technical and design detail. **Target System** and **Hardware** specify the intended platform and technical requirements. **Game Mechanics** outlines the primary systems governing player interaction, while **Gameplay** offers a comprehensive explanation of how these mechanics function within the player experience. **Graphics and Audio** elaborates on the visual and auditory identity of the game, and finally, **Narrative** provides a brief overview of the story underpinning the experience.

To understand the full context of this document, it is recommended to read the glossary of common video game terminology and acronyms.

Glossary

Collaboration between the entertainment video game industry and the wider cultural sectors often presents communication challenges arising from differing professional languages and organisational structures (Klimas et al., 2025b). To address these challenges, this section of the document provides definitions of key terminology commonly used in video game development. By establishing a shared vocabulary, this glossary serves as a neutral reference point intended to mitigate potential misunderstandings and facilitate clearer communication among project partners. This effort builds upon research conducted during the Design Thinking Marathons (DTthons) organised by Wrocław University of Economics and Business, which identified key areas where terminology gaps hinder effective cross-sectoral collaboration.

It should be noted that feedback regarding the clarity and utility of this CDD, as well as the accompanying Game Design Documentation (GDD), is currently being gathered from project's cultural partners. While a comprehensive analysis of this feedback falls outside the scope of this document, the insights collected may inform future collaborative efforts and serve as a foundation for refining documentation practices in subsequent projects.

An overview of commonly used video game terminology and acronyms includes:

DOCUMENTATION AND PROCESS

- ♥ **CDD (Concept Design Document)** – A brief overview highlighting the core idea and vision of the game.
- ♥ **GDD (Game Design Document)** – A more detailed document containing technical specifications.
- ♥ **Pre-production** – Planning phase of game development in which the concept is explored, along with the creation of prototypes and a visual direction before the full development begins.
- ♥ **Production** – The main development phase where the game is actively built by artists, programmers, designers and audio specialists.
- ♥ **Post-production** – The phase after the development focusing on bug fixes, optimisation, maintenance and often marketing.
- ♥ **Prototype** – An early or experimental version of a game to test whether an idea works before committing full resources.

DESIGN & PLAYER

- ♥ **Core game loop** – The main activities a player repeats throughout the game.
- ♥ **Mechanics** – The rules determining what actions a player can take and what happens as a result of these actions.
- ♥ **Gameplay** – The overall experience and feeling of playing the game, shaped by how all the rules, challenges and pacing work together to evoke a feeling.
- ♥ **Traversal puzzles** – Challenges solved by the player figuring out how to physically move through a space.
- ♥ **Player (character)** – The character directly controlled by the player in the game.
- ♥ **NPC (Non-Player Character)** – Any character in the game controlled by the computer rather than the player.
- ♥ **Single-player** – A game designed to be played by one person without multiplayer functionalities.
- ♥ **Environmental storytelling** – Conveying the narrative through the game world itself rather than dialogue with characters, text or cutscenes.

INPUT AND HARDWARE

- ♥ **Gamepad or Controller** – A handheld device with buttons and joysticks used to control games.
- ♥ **D-pad (Directional pad)** – A flat, often cross-shaped button on a controller used for input in four or eight directions.
- ♥ **Joystick or Analogue stick** – Small thumb stick on a controller that registers direction and degree of movement.
- ♥ **Analogue input** – Input that registers a range of values rather than simply the on or off state.

VISUAL AND ART

- ♥ **Art direction** – the overarching vision guiding all visual decision to create a cohesive aesthetic for the game.
- ♥ **Poly or Polygon** – The basic geometric shaped, usually triangular, that combine to form the 3D models used in games.
- ♥ **Low-poly, Medium-poly or High-poly** – A description of how much geometric detail a 3D model contains.
- ♥ **Textures** – Textures are 2D images applied to 3D models to give them surface detail, colour and material appearance.

- ♥ **Dynamic lighting** – Lighting that changes in real time based on game events, time of day, seasons and player actions.
- ♥ **Particle effects** – Visual effects made of many small elements (sparks, smoke or dust for example).
- ♥ **Fog layers** – Atmospheric visual effects that obscure distant objects, adding depth and mood to environments.
- ♥ **Visual motifs** – Recurring visual elements that carry thematic meaning or guide the player's attention and navigation.

AUDIO

- ♥ **SFX (Sound Effects)** – Non-musical audio. For example: footsteps, impacts, ambient sounds and character vocalisations.
- ♥ **Reverb** – An audio effect simulating how sounds reflects and decays within a physical environment.

3. About the Concept

The information in this Concept Design Document is a result of the concept creation that emerged from collaborative discussions with the three cultural partners: the London Symphony Orchestra (LSO), the Imperial War Museum (IWM) and City Football Group (CFG), and the developers of the game at Breda University of Applied Sciences (BUAs), in collaboration with the Target Audience researchers at the University of Salford (USAL). The three cultural partners aligned on expanding their reach to younger and more diverse audiences, yet each brought different creative priorities to the project: personal wartime stories for the IWM, immersive musical and emotional experiences for the LSO, and sports-centred gaming for the CFG.

These different perspectives prompted the BUAs team to identify shared themes that could unite our partners. To achieve this, the academic partners (USAL and the Wrocław University of Economics and Business) and the cultural partners (LSO, IWM and CFG) came together to participate in an online ideation session. This highlighted shared themes that resonated across the three cultural institutions:

- ♥ Growth through overcoming adversity
- ♥ Exploring physical spaces, history, and interpersonal relationships
- ♥ Collaborative play prioritising community-building over competition
- ♥ Learning new skills and knowledge through gameplay
- ♥ Creating meaningful experiences within a larger narrative.

Drawing inspiration from both the cultural partners' initial ideas and the shared themes that emerged from the ideation session, the development team at BUAs then conducted a concept jam in September 2025. Here, the GAMEHEARTS team worked on a set of video game concepts to guide the final design that will be developed. The combined effort of the programmers, artists, and designers is essential to creating a complete and well-rounded concept using creative frameworks such as the Double Diamond method, ideation tools and the Crazy Eight brainstorming method. During the Concept Jam, the development team worked in two separate groups across two days, where each team explored a variety of video game concepts. This was narrowed down to one final game concept, ready to be further defined in the next phase of concepting.

In addition to the cultural partner's unique themes, priorities, and constraints, findings from both the Target Audience Research by the researchers from University of Salford and the insights from the Design Thinking Marathons conducted by the Wrocław University of Economics and Business were presented to the developers at BUAs. These insights were used to define the concept over the course of three months. The game concept, as documented in this CDD, was presented at the GAMEHEARTS Conference at the Imperial War Museum in London in October 2025.

The concept as part of GAMEHEARTS

The GAMEHEARTS project aims to maximise the value of the European video game industry ecosystems (EVGIE) within a wider social context of the creative and cultural industries (CCI). Exploring and creating 'ludic experiences' is part of that goal, as ways to develop more inclusive, engaging, and empowering cultural experiences. As both the EVGIE and the CCI are at the heart of this project, the 'ludic experience' to be developed, would result from the collaboration between the two industries. As most creative processes, the creation of the 'ludic experience', or game/advanced prototype, starts with the concepting phase. The concept addresses the aims of the project in the following ways:

♥ Demonstrating viable collaboration

The concept emerged from structured dialogue between the game developers at BUAs and the three cultural partners: the London Symphony Orchestra (LSO), the Imperial War Museum (IWM) and City Football Group (CFG). Rather than treating cultural content to be extracted and adapted, the development process positioned cultural partners as active collaborators whose priorities shaped the concept from the start. The resulting design reflects a negotiated vision that balanced each partner's unique themes, priorities, and constraints with the practical constraints of game development.

♥ Exploring audience expansion

Each cultural partner identified reaching younger and more diverse audiences as a strategic priority. The concept responds to these shared goals by embedding cultural content within an accessible, emotionally engaging experience. The game does not ask players to appreciate orchestral music, wartime history, or football culture in isolation, but rather weaves these elements into a cohesive journey where cultural engagement emerges naturally from gameplay. This approach tests whether games can serve as pathways to cultural institutions rather than replacements for them.

♥ Integrating diverse cultural domains

A key challenge in the project in the GAMEHEARTS project is how distinct cultural sections such as performing arts, heritage institutions, sports organisations, and video games might find common ground within a single interactive experience. The concept addresses this by identifying shared thematic territory, such as human resilience in difficult times, a feeling of community and hope. By translating each partner's priorities into complementary design elements, in this case the rhythm-based mechanics driven by orchestral music, the setting informed by civilian life during wartimes and the protagonist of the game embodying play, community, and a sense of belonging.

The concept serves the base and core idea for the next phase in the project: the development of the video game prototype and will serve as an aid in the communication between the development team at BUAs and the cultural partners at London Symphony Orchestra, City Football Group, and Imperial War Museum. As a concept document, this deliverable represents a snapshot of the design intentions rather than the tested product. The claims made about the audience engagement, cultural integration, and collaborative benefit remain propositional until the concept is developed into a playable prototype and evaluated through player research as outlined in work package 6.

Informed concept

While the previous sections describe the collaborative process that informed the concept, this section identifies how specific research findings shaped the design decisions. The CDD is not just a creative brief; it is a design informed by insights, frameworks, and structured investigation.

Although collective insights from across the GAMEHEARTS project have shaped the overall concept, the design constraints and user personas were directly informed by the Target Audience Research conducted by the University of Salford and the Insights from the Design Thinking Marathon conducted by Wrocław University of Economics and Business. The Target Audience Research informed the development of four user personas and revealed the Explorer and Achiever player motivations (based on Bartle's Taxonomy of Player Types (Richard a. Bartle: Players Who Suit MUDs, n.d.)), which shaped the decisions about game structure, the emphasis on discovery over completion, and accessibility features designed to reach younger and more diverse audiences. The Design Thinking Marathons identified terminology gaps and expectation misalignments between the EVGIE and CCI, which prompted the inclusion of a glossary, the document's use of language and earlier concept presentations showcased to the GAMEHEARTS partners.

Each cultural partner's priorities functioned as design constraints: the Imperial War Museum's focus on personal wartime stories led to wordless narrative and environmental storytelling that emphasises civilian experience; the London Symphony Orchestra's emphasis on immersive musical experiences shaped the rhythm-based core mechanics and integration of orchestral music directly into gameplay; and City Football Group's sports-centred engagement inspired the football protagonist and themes of teamwork, community and belonging. Rather than watering down any of these visions, common ground was found that let each partner's priorities shine through.

Concept as culture

Rolling ball games have been part of video game culture for decades. Among many other possible examples, in the 1980s there was the precision platforming of *Marble Madness* (1984), then later came the fast-paced gameplay of *Super Monkey Ball* (2001), the zany story and experimentation of *Katamari Damacy* (2004), and the competitive chaos of *Kabounce* (2018) which was released by a company based in Breda. Before these, some of the earliest digital elements in games were on physical pinball tables. Players have long found joy in guiding a ball through challenging environments. The concept of the GAMEHEARTS experience draws on that same enjoyment, including the satisfying physics of rolling, jumping, and navigating obstacles, given fresh context and inspiration from the cultural partners. What sets this game apart from other games is not the ball itself, but what the ball represents and the world it moves through. By partnering with the LSO, the IWM, and CFG, the concept is transformed into an emotional journey through wartime landscapes, driven by orchestral music and carrying the themes of loss, hope, and reunion with one's community. The cultural partnerships do not simply add a layer of polish; they give the core mechanics meaning. Rolling, evading, and jumping on the rhythm becomes a way of experiencing orchestral music. Navigating the environment becomes a way of witnessing history and the civilian impact of wartime. The ball's journey home becomes a story about resilience and belonging. In this way, the concept honours its video game heritage while reaching for something that ball-rolling games have rarely attempted: genuine emotional depth rooted in real cultural institutions.

Target audience

The target audience describes the players the game is designed for, which are the people most likely to enjoy and benefit from the experience. This audience was identified through Target Audience Research conducted by the University of Salford (USAL), which examined the preferences, motivations, and the kinds of people the cultural partners most wanted to reach. Four user personas were developed to embody the target audience, drawing on research findings, the wants and wishes of the three cultural partners, and established video game industry frameworks, specifically Bartle's Taxonomy of Player Types (Bartle, 1996).

The game primarily caters to the Explorer and Achiever player types: those who enjoy discovering new worlds and stories at their own pace, and those motivated by goals and a sense of accomplishment. Each persona reflects a different cultural partner connection: Joan the War Historian seeks the emotional depth valued by the Imperial War Museum, William the Casual Rhythm Appreciator enjoys the immersive musical experiences preferred by the London Symphony Orchestra and Erling the Football Fan shared the passion for sports central in City Football Group. Lastly, Maddy, the Game Creator-Player represents the game industry perspective on meaningful cultural collaboration.

PERSONA 1: JOAN, THE WAR HISTORIAN

Joan is interested in the human side of war. They seek a deep emotional connection between the current times and the past, which is reflected in the games they enjoy playing.

Player type: *Explorer/Socialiser*. They aim to completely immerse themselves in new worlds, companions (NPCs) and the lore of the game. They like to discover the world and its story at their own pace, which is why attention to detail, and storytelling is important to this player type. While this type is both explorer and socialiser, as they like to play and enjoy music with others, the focus remains on the casual exploration rather than intensive social gameplay.

Goal(s): The Casual Rhythm Appreciator wants an engaging storyline and a relaxing and casual experience when they play games. Gaming is a form of escapism from the bouts of daily life, while they are also open to new and engaging worlds to explore, learn from, or just visit. While music and audio design are important, they are not the first thing they look for when selecting a game to play.

Barrier(s): The game needs to be an emotional experience rather than an educational one, while still informative enough to satisfy the War Historian's curiosity. As the game needs to be for all audiences, the type of content also matters, as it needs to refrain from any potentially harmful depictions of war.

PERSONA 2: WILLIAM, THE CASUAL RHYTHM APPRECIATOR

William is a casual lover of music. They listen to a variety of music in their free time, from video game tracks to electronic to classical music.

Player type: *Explorer/Socialiser*. They aim to completely immerse themselves in new worlds, companions (NPCs) and the lore of the game. They like to discover the world and its story at their own pace, which is why attention to detail, and storytelling is important to this player type. While this type is both explorer and socialiser, as they like to play and enjoy music with others, the focus remains on the casual exploration rather than intensive social gameplay.

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Barrier(s): The game needs to be challenging while remaining casual. The Casual Rhythm Appreciator does not shy away from a challenge, but the time spent on these challenges needs to be short or broken up by sequences of exploration for it to be a relaxing experience.

PERSONA 3: ERLING, THE FOOTBALL FAN

Erling is a youthful, passionate fan of football, and their favourite club is Manchester City. They like playing games and enjoy friendly, but passionate, competition with their peers.

Player type: *Achiever/Socialiser*. They aim to accomplish a goal in the game, often through completion of the game or gathering (cosmetic) rewards. The ‘socialiser’ part is expressed through their need for feeling part of a community through gaming.

Goal(s): The Football Fan wants a goal to work towards and does not shy away from a challenge. The games they play ideally are related to their beloved sport. They also want to feel connected to the game and the players they revere (such as Pep Guardiola, Erling Haaland, Sergio Agüero, and Yaya Touré) on a deeper level.

Barrier(s): The game needs to reflect the love and passion they have for their favourite club. They prefer active gameplay over a more passive approach (such as abstract puzzles). They want depth and a sense of community in a game that does not get boring quickly.

PERSONA 4: MADDY, THE GAME CREATOR-PLAYER

Maddy is a passionate developer who enjoys playing a variety of games and visiting cultural institutions in their free time.

Player type: *Explorer/Achiever*. The Game Creator-Player aims to create and play engaging and innovative games that can translate cultural narratives into mechanics, dynamics, and aesthetics. Using innovative approaches to collaboration, (visual) storytelling and level design, the Game Creator-Player demonstrates that challenge and casual exploration are not mutually exclusive.

Goal(s): To create and experience games that show how cultural values can authentically enhance interactive storytelling and gameplay without becoming po-faced, serious games, or edutainment. The game needs to be a genuinely compelling experience that has both cultural and industry significance.

Barrier(s): They are aware that a portion of the culturally themed games might feel shallow or educational rather than entertaining or engaging. The posed constraints could also lead these games to be less innovative technically or gameplaywise. The Game Creator-Player will have to avoid treating culture as a decoration but instead implement it in its core gameplay.

ACCESSIBILITY AND INCLUSION

Accessibility was considered from the earliest stages of the project. The shared goal of reaching younger and more diverse audiences meant the concept needed to welcome players who might not typically engage with cultural content or (video) games. This commitment shaped discussions with the cultural partners and within the development team and informed the themes and tone of the concept before any design work began.

Other design decisions were also made with accessibility in mind. The wordless narrative removes the language barriers, allowing players from different backgrounds to follow the story. The dual structure of the Highway and Vignette levels offers varied pacing, so players can experience moments of intensity balanced with calmer exploration. The camera and movement systems were designed to minimise motion sickness, which is a common issue in games features rolling or continuous movement. The design counters these issues by keeping the player character centred, limited sudden camera shifts and creating distinct alternating textures, as to prevent nausea or other motion sickness symptoms for both the player and the surrounding audience.

Accessibility was also kept in mind in the decisions surrounding hardware and software. The game targets a PC with gamepad controls, which is a widely accessible set-up that avoids costs of dedicated gaming consoles. The minimum hardware specifications are set at mid-range level to ensure the game runs on computers that many players, or cultural partners, already own. Lastly, the engine chosen provides built-in accessibility feature that the developers can draw on during production, as well as the simple control scheme (movement, jumping, chiming) keeps the game approachable for players less familiar with complex input systems and video games. The simple control scheme also allows for an easy swap with accessibility-specific controllers such as the Xbox Adaptive Controller if required.

4. Game Concept Overview

Game Concept

The game is a rhythm-based environmental adventure about a football separated from its family during wartime. Set in a semi-realistic landscape inspired by both World Wars, players control the ball through warzones, abandoned towns, and wooded highlands by moving and jumping to music. The game aims to show civilian hardships during wartime while keeping gameplay fun and engaging. Players solve environmental puzzles and use rhythm-based movement to progress through levels, with each area's music reflecting different parts of the journey. The game tells its story without words, using music and the visuals along the ball's path from separation to reunion with its family. By combining rhythm gameplay with puzzle-solving, the game offers a different perspective on the human cost of war.

Genre

The genre of the game is rhythm-based environmental adventure.

Setting

The game is set in a semi-realistic world influenced by early to mid-20th century wartime. The events and locations are intended to reflect European history during wartime without being a direct representation of any specific place or event.

Game structure

The game world is split into three main areas or 'acts': Battlefield, Town, and Wooded Highlands. Each of these acts contains multiple smaller zones that can be divided into two types of gameplay: Highway levels and Vignette levels.

In the Highway levels, the player moves through the level design on the rhythm of music and in the Vignette levels the player can explore the environment and solve traversal puzzles. The Highway levels alternate with the Vignette levels, and each act will contain at least one of both. The player will move through these locations in a linear manner, following the story arc.

Player

The player will control an early 20th century style football through a single-player experience. Being a single-player game limits the scope of production, reduces the need for post-production server hosting, and increases the ease of testing in multiple locations without complex networking.

Core game loop

The game uses continuous movement to propel the player (as the ball) forward throughout the whole game. Players will be able to move left and right, speed up, slow down, and jump. Later in the game, the additional mechanic of chiming will be introduced as an additional interaction with the environment.

Look and feel

The game's art direction emphasises high-contrast visuals, with strong use of shadows and vivid and high-saturation colours. Recognisable shapes and bold silhouettes ensure clarity and identity, while fog layers add depth and intrigue. Animation leans heavily on particle effects and environmental movement, making the world feel alive and reactive while keeping the game within the production scope. The living environment and progression of time is further emphasised with distinct seasons that are assigned to each of the acts. Moving between fall, winter, and spring diversifies the aesthetics during the game. A central focus is on building mood and atmosphere by connecting audio cues with dynamic lighting setups. Because the game is designed to emulate the feelings, experiences, and emotions of a person in wartime, both the visual style and audio of the game will enhance those feelings throughout the different acts, showing the devastating implications of war while maintaining a sense of hope throughout the player's journey.

Figure 1 - Concept design by Marie Lhuissier-Hutchinson for the trenches to show the look and feel of the game

5. Target System

The game will be developed for one platform: PC (Personal Computer) and will use a gamepad to play. This allows industry-standard controls and easier implementation plus testing by GAMEHEARTS partners.

Target Hardware

We target a mid-range platform using the following minimum specifications:

- ♥ Ryzen 5 7600x
- ♥ Radeon 7600XT
- ♥ 16gb ram
- ♥ 50gb storage

Gamepad

The game is played using a gamepad (controller), focusing on the Xbox One controller layout as a design standard. It is important that the gamepad contains at least one joystick or D-pad with two buttons for the movement of the ball and interaction with the environment. An additional joystick can be used for camera interaction if available on the controller.

6. Software

The game will be developed using Unreal Engine 5, version 5.7. Other tools will include but are not limited to:

- ♥ Houdini
- ♥ FMOD
- ♥ Reaper
- ♥ Blender
- ♥ Photoshop

7. Mechanics

Core mechanics

- ♥ **Character Controls** - Horizontal control, jumping, and adjusting the rolling speed of the continuously moving ball
- ♥ **Chime** - Emit musical chimes that resonate with the environment to solve puzzles and communicate with companions
- ♥ **Inflation and deflation** - Inflate or deflate to alter bounce height, rolling speed and the ability to squeeze through small gaps

- ♥ **Rhythm based** - Navigate through levels by timing movements, jumps, and evasions to the music. Interact with objects throughout the environment to add to the melody
- ♥ **Puzzle and traversal** - Solve puzzles using precise navigation, momentum, and objects to activate pressure plates and buttons to open paths.

8. Gameplay

Objectives

The main objective is for our protagonist (the ball) to reunite with their family. To do this, the player will traverse through the three acts to escape the ongoing war, discover the powers of sport and music, and reach a place where life can begin again.

Progression

The game is meant to provide a sense of progression in two ways. First is the **Progression of Time**, where the player should feel like the journey they embark on takes longer than the actual playtime of the game. This is done by changing of seasons and environmental storytelling. Secondly, the **Progression towards your Goal** is where we give the player a sense of direction and achievement. This is achieved through visual motifs and symbols that guide the players through the acts. Audio effects, particles, and recognisable tokens of hope and origin (for example, poppy flowers that the family bring along). Parts of this are the Vignette areas, which are traversal puzzles where players trigger progression to the game's next zone.

Player character

The player character is represented by a football, belonging to a family with two young children from a small countryside village. The design of the football is inspired by footballs used in the early half of the 20th century, using time accurate materials and colour schemes. The football expresses emotions such as sadness, fear, and playfulness through art and SFX (Sound Effects).

Character Actions

CHARACTER MOVEMENT

The player can adjust the trajectory of the ball by moving left and right using analogue input for smooth directional control. Players can also accelerate and decelerate to change the momentum of the ball, allowing precise speed management for different challenges. A jump action provides upwards velocity for vertical movement.

ENVIRONMENTAL INTERACTIONS

♥ Chime

The chime action emits audio that triggers environmental objects and characters (NPCs). This serves as the primary non-physical interaction method.

♥ Environmental Actions

Items can be collected naturally by rolling over them, requiring no additional input from the player. The ball's weight also naturally activates pressure plates on contact, and direct impact from the ball activates buttons and switches in the environment. Momentum gained from accelerating and decelerating can be used to push movable objects.

9. Graphics and Audio

Visuals

The game employs a hybrid art style, combining 3D foreground assets with 2D background elements. All interactive gameplay elements, including the player character, interactive objects, and the direct environment are rendered in 3D to provide depth and dynamic lighting. Environmental backgrounds are created using 2D layers to enhance the atmosphere and optimise performance.

We use a stylised medium-poly (polygon) approach for the 3D models, similar to games like *Firewatch* and the *Legend of Zelda: Breath of the Wild* (table 1). Models feature simplified details and textures while maintaining realistic proportions and avoid both overly rounded cartoon styles and angular low-poly aesthetics where everything appears triangular. We aim to use recognisable shapes with bold silhouettes that build strong compositions, which will enhance the visual storytelling and naturally guide players through each area.

Inspiration for seasonal changes

Inspiration for art style

Table 1 - Inspiration for the seasonal changes (left) and inspiration for art style (right). Images left column (top to bottom): Robin Tran on Artstation (2025), Katelyn Johnson on Artstation (2025) for the game God of War Ragnarök (2022), The Legend of Zelda: Breath of the Wild (2017). Images right column (top to bottom): Firewatch (2016), Firewatch (2016), and Journey (2012).

Audio

MUSIC

The game will feature orchestral music from our cultural partners at the London Symphony Orchestra, bringing depth and emotional resonance to the experience. The musical themes evolve based on locations throughout the acts, with distinct pieces to set the mood and feeling as the story progresses. The Highway levels integrate rhythm-based gameplay directly tied to the LSO's melodies, where the player and environment sync with the music, creating a unique fusion of orchestral music and gameplay mechanics.

SOUND EFFECTS

The ball's sounds, such as rolling, bouncing, sliding, and hitting objects, help convey emotion throughout gameplay. We aim to adjust sound properties to create different feelings: high-pitched, fast, and bright sounds for happy or playful moments, while low-pitched, slow, and muffled sounds for sad or tense situations. Different surfaces and spaces will affect these sounds through reverb and texture variations. Sound will react to player actions in real-time, changing based on the ball's speed, impact strength, and what surface it is rolling on. This audio feedback helps players feel connected to their actions and understand the game state. By linking physics to sound, we will create a dynamic audio system where the ball's movements produce expressive sounds that support both gameplay mechanics and emotional moments.

10. Story and Narrative

Backstory

The player plays as a little football that is owned by the two younger children in a family of florists. They live in a small village and sell their flowers. As war emerges, they must flee toward a safer place, further from the frontlines. Being a treasured toy to the children, the little football gets loaded into their truck to travel to the family farm.

Main Plot

The game will use a 3-act play structure for the main story. The starting act is one of loss and fear as the football gets separated from the family and needs to flee the dangers of war. The second act focuses on finding companionship and purpose while traversing the war-ridden world. The third, and final act, highlights hope and community as the football will have to overcome the final adversities to reunite with the family.

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